

Social Media Addiction and Psychological Well-Being: The Moderating Roles of Need for Social Approval and Extraversion

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Abstract

The rapid rise of social networking sites has raised concerns about their implications for mental health. While the link between problematic use and diminished psychological well-being is well-known, the specific personality profiles that exacerbate this risk remain underexplored. This study examined the moderating roles of the need for social approval and extraversion in the relationship between social media addiction and psychological well-being. A sample of 304 university students completed the Social Media Addiction Scale, Need for Social Approval Scale, Basic Personality Traits Inventory, and Psychological Well-Being Scale. The results indicated that social media addiction significantly predicts lower well-being. Moderation analyses revealed that this negative relationship was significantly stronger for individuals with a high need for social approval, creating a “validation trap.” Furthermore, contrary to the “rich-get-richer” hypothesis, high extraversion also strengthened the negative association of addiction, supporting the social displacement hypothesis. Consequently, the findings suggest that the negative association between digital dependency and psychological well-being is particularly strong for extraverted individuals and those seeking external validation, as it likely displaces face-to-face interaction and fosters anxiety.

Keywords: Digital Dependence, Health Psychology, Problematic Internet Use, Social Displacement, Social Psychology.

Sosyal Medya Bağımlılığı ve Psikolojik İyi Oluş: Sosyal Onay İhtiyacı ve Dışadönüklüğün Düzenleyici Rollerini

Özet

Sosyal ağ sitelerinin hızla yaygınlaşması, bunların ruh sağlığı üzerindeki etkilerine dair endişeleri artırmıştır. Problemleri kullanım ile azalan psikolojik iyi oluş arasındaki bağlantı iyi bilinmesine rağmen bu riski artıran özgül kişilik profilleri yeterince araştırılmamıştır. Bu çalışmada, sosyal medya bağımlılığı ile psikolojik iyi oluş arasındaki ilişkide sosyal onay ihtiyacı ve dışadönüklüğün düzenleyici rolleri incelenmiştir. 304 üniversite öğrencisinden oluşan örneklem; Sosyal Medya Bağımlılığı Ölçeği, Sosyal Onay İhtiyacı Ölçeği, Temel Kişilik Özellikleri Envanteri ve Psikolojik İyi Oluş Ölçeğini doldurmuştur. Sonuçlar, sosyal medya bağımlılığının düşük iyi oluşu anlamlı düzeyde yordadığını göstermiştir. Düzenleyicilik analizleri, bu negatif ilişkinin sosyal onay ihtiyacı yüksek bireylerde anlamlı derecede daha güçlü olduğunu ve bir “onay tuzağı” yarattığını ortaya koymuştur. Ayrıca, “zengin daha da zenginleşir” hipotezinin aksine, yüksek dışadönüklük de bağımlılığın negatif ilişkisini güçlendirerek sosyal yer değiştirme hipotezini desteklemiştir. Sonuç olarak bulgular; dijital bağımlılık ile psikolojik iyi oluş arasındaki negatif ilişkinin, muhtemelen yüz yüze etkileşimin yerini alması ve kaygıyı beslemesi nedeniyle, özellikle dışadönük ve dışsal onay arayan bireylerde daha güçlü olduğuna işaret etmektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Dijital Bağımlılık, Sağlık Psikolojisi, Problemleri İnternet Kullanımı, Sosyal Yer Değiştirme, Sosyal Psikoloji.

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We are experiencing a digital shift that has fundamentally changed the ways in which we interact and socialize. Today, social media platforms are more than simple digital tools; they are integrated within the daily routines and practices of billions of people (Kuss & Griffiths, 2017). This reality is clearly evident in Türkiye, where recent statistics illustrate that the internet usage of young people is almost fully saturated (TÜİK, 2024). For social media platforms to serve as tools for connection, users must be able to control how much time they spend on them. Unfortunately, social media is designed to keep users engaged in a continuous cycle of scrolling and interaction. Consequently, this design causes some users to lose control over their usage. This phenomenon, attracting increasing research interest, is termed ‘social media addiction’ in the literature (Andreassen, 2015).

However, labeling this problematic usage solely as a clinical issue risks missing the broader picture. Therefore, it is important to clarify where this study stands theoretically. Although the term “addiction” is used, the subject is approached here through the lens of health and social psychology, rather than strictly clinical psychiatry. Problematic social media use is viewed not necessarily as severe clinical pathology, but rather as a behavioral pattern existing on a continuum of habit strength (ranging from adaptive, moderate use to maladaptive, compulsive engagement) that interacts with a person’s daily functioning. Within the health psychology framework, the primary focus is psychological well-being. The focus is less on symptom reduction and more on how digital habits either support or erode a flourishing life. By integrating social motives, it is also acknowledged that what we do online is often a manifestation of deep-seated human needs, such as the desire for acceptance, thereby anchoring this work in social psychology.

Theoretical Framework: I-PACE Model and Moderator Variables

To understand the stakes, we must look at the empirical landscape. There is a substantial body of evidence linking problematic social media use to poorer mental health. Large-scale studies

have consistently shown that as addiction tendencies rise, psychological well-being tends to fall (Marino et al., 2018; Twenge & Campbell, 2019). Excessive use is frequently tied to anxiety (Vannucci et al., 2017), depression (Hunt et al., 2018), fatigue (Dhir et al., 2018), and a paradoxical sense of social isolation (Primack et al., 2017). The displacement hypothesis offers a common explanation for this: time spent on screens is simply time stolen from face-to-face interactions or other activities that nurture us (Kuss & Griffiths, 2017).

Yet, this transition from heavy use to diminished well-being is not a uniform process; it does not happen to everyone in the same way. To map these individual differences, Brand et al. (2016) proposed the Interaction of Person-Affect-Cognition-Execution (I-PACE) model. This framework suggests that internet-use behaviors are the product of an interaction between a person's core characteristics and specific triggers. Following this logic, the simultaneous influence of two critical "person" variables is examined: the need for social approval and extraversion. While distinct, these two constructs work in tandem online; one drives the hunger for social stimulation (extraversion), while the other dictates how sensitive we are to the feedback we receive (need for approval).

The need for social approval is essentially a dispositional tendency to seek validation and an acute sensitivity to rejection (Karaşar & Öğülmüş, 2016). According to social comparison theory (Festinger, 1954), individuals have an innate drive to evaluate their own standing by comparing themselves to others. For individuals with a high need for approval, social media functions as a *validation marketplace*, a digital environment where self-worth is continuously quantified, sought, and exchanged through visible metrics such as likes, comments, and follower counts. It triggers intense social comparison processes, where upward comparisons (seeing others' idealized lives) can breed feelings of inadequacy (Vogel et al., 2014). It is argued that for someone high in this need, well-being becomes dangerously

contingent on external likes and comments, making the impact of addiction far more severe than it is for someone with an internal sense of worth.

The second moderator, extraversion, reflects one's level of sociability and assertiveness (Gençöz & Öncül, 2012). Its role in digital well-being is debated. While some argue extraverts benefit from online tools (rich-get-richer), the social displacement hypothesis suggests otherwise. Since extraverts thrive on genuine, face-to-face energy, substituting that with screen time is psychologically costly (Primack et al., 2017). Essentially, it is posited that high extraversion might act as a vulnerability factor when paired with addictive use, simply because the "opportunity cost" of missing offline life is higher for them than for introverts.

Guided by social comparison theory, social displacement hypothesis, and I-PACE model, this study moves beyond asking if social media harms well-being, to asking for whom the risk is highest. Specifically, within the I-PACE framework, the current study focuses on how predisposing "Person" (P) characteristics, such as the personality trait of extraversion and the core social motive of need for social approval, interact with the "Execution" (E) of problematic behaviors (i.e., social media addiction) to diminish psychological well-being. Accordingly, the following interaction hypotheses are tested:

Hypothesis 1: Need for social approval moderates the negative relationship between social media addiction and psychological well-being, such that this negative association is stronger for individuals with a high need for social approval.

Hypothesis 2: Extraversion moderates the negative relationship between social media addiction and psychological well-being, such that this negative association is stronger for highly extraverted individuals.

Hypothesis 3: The negative relationship between social media addiction and psychological well-being is most pronounced among individuals who exhibit both high extraversion and a high need for social approval.

Methods

Participants and Procedure

To ensure sufficient statistical power to detect the hypothesized interaction effects, a priori power analysis was conducted using G*Power 3.1.9.7. Based on a targeted medium effect size ($f^2 = .15$) with an alpha level of .05 and 95% power, the analysis indicated a minimum requirement of 138 participants. The final sample size was kept above this threshold to account for potential data loss and to increase the robustness of the moderation analyses. The sample consisted of 304 university students studying in Türkiye. The mean age of the participants was 21.6 (aged 18-51, $SD = 2.91$). Regarding gender distribution, 231 participants identified as female (89.8%), 31 identified as male (10.2%). The participants were distributed across different years of study: 82 were in their first year (27%), 94 in their second year (30.9%), 35 in their third year (11.5%), and 93 in their fourth year or above (30.6%). In terms of marital status, most of the sample was single ($n = 300$, 98.7%), while 4 participants were married.

Data collection was carried out using the convenience sampling method. Participants were approached in classroom settings and invited to complete an online survey. Before participation, all students were provided with an informed consent form detailing the study's purpose, the anonymity of their data, and their right to withdraw. The average completion time was approximately 15 minutes. Ethical approval for this study was granted by the local ethical committee of the university.

Measures

Informed Consent and Demographic Information

Before the study, an informed consent form was presented to participants, ensuring they understood that participation was entirely voluntary and they had the right to withdraw at any

moment without consequence. After providing consent, they were asked to report basic demographic details, including age, gender, and year of study.

Social Media Addiction Scale (SMAS)

Social media addiction was measured using the Social Media Addiction Scale developed by Firat and Barut (2018). This 24-item scale consists of two sub-dimensions: deprivation and uncontrollability. Items are rated on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = never, 5 = always). In the original development study, the scale showed strong internal consistency, with Cronbach's alpha coefficients of .86 for deprivation, .90 for uncontrollability, and .93 for the total scale. Construct validity was supported by confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) fit indices, $\chi^2 = 469.86$, $df = 249$, $p < .001$, AGFI = .91, GFI = .90, CFI = .93, TLI = .92, SRMR = .047, RMSEA = .052.

Extraversion Measure

Personality traits were measured using the Extraversion subscale of the Basic Personality Traits Scale, developed for the Turkish culture by Gençöz and Öncül (2012). Items are rated on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = not at all appropriate, 5 = completely appropriate). The scale originally had 8 items, and this factor showed high reliability in the source study, with a reported Cronbach's alpha of .89.

Need for Social Approval Scale (NFSAS)

To measure sensitivity to external validation, the Need for Social Approval Scale (Karaşar & Öğülmüş, 2016) was used. This 25-item tool includes three sub-dimensions: sensitivity to others' judgments, social withdrawal, and leaving a good impression. Higher scores show a stronger dependency on approval. Items are rated on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree). The original study reported alpha coefficients of .83, .80, and .80 for the sub-dimensions, and .90 for the total scale. Construct validity was confirmed with

adequate fit indices, $\chi^2 = 573.93$, $df = 272$, CFI = .95, NFI = .90, NNFI = .94, IFI = .95, RMR = .06, RMSEA = .06.

Psychological Well-Being Scale (PWBS)

Psychological functioning was assessed via the Psychological Well-Being Scale (Diener et al., 2010), adapted into Turkish by Telef (2013). This 8-item measure provides a summary of psychosocial resources. Items are rated on a 7-point Likert scale (1= strongly disagree, 7 = strongly agree). The adaptation study reported a Cronbach's alpha of .80, and CFA results showed satisfactory construct validity, $\chi^2 = 92.90$, $df = 20$, $p < .001$, GFI = .96, CFI = .95, IFI = .95, NFI = .94, RFI = .92, SRMR = .04, RMSEA = .08.

Data Analysis

Data analysis was performed using JAMOVI (Version 2.4.14) in a two-step process. First, the psychometric properties of the measures were tested again within the current sample using CFA with the Weighted Least Squares Mean and Variance adjusted (WLSMV) estimator, which is specifically recommended for ordinal data (Hair et al., 2014; Tabachnick & Fidell, 2013). Second, to test the main hypotheses, moderation analyses were conducted using the "GAMLj3" module in JAMOVI. Specifically, the interactions of social media addiction (SMA) with extraversion (EXT) and need for social approval (NFSA) on psychological well-being (PWB) were examined in one model.

Results

Preliminary Analyses: Psychometric Validation

Before proceeding to hypothesis testing, a series of tests was conducted to verify the validity and reliability of the scales within the current sample. Validity was assessed using CFA, while reliability and convergent validity were evaluated using Composite Reliability (CR) and Average Variance Extracted (AVE). For the CFA, model fit was examined using indices such

as CFI (comparative fit index), TLI (Tucker-Lewis index), SRMR (standardized root mean square residual), and RMSEA (root mean square error of approximation).

To address potential common method bias (CMB) inherent in self-report designs, both procedural and statistical remedies were implemented (Podsakoff et al., 2003). Procedurally, anonymity was guaranteed and participants were informed that there were no right or wrong answers to minimize evaluation apprehension. Statistically, Harman's single-factor test revealed multiple factors, with the largest accounting for 24.14% of the total variance. Since no single factor explained a majority of the variance (i.e., <50%), CMB was not considered a significant threat to the validity of the findings.

During the CFA of the Extraversion measure, it was observed that Item 2 (cold) displayed a very weak factor loading ($\beta = .28$). Consequently, this item was removed, and the scale was used with 7 items. Additionally, due to high modification indices (18.4), error terms were allowed to correlate between item 3 (shy) and item 8 (timid).

A two-step CFA approach was applied for the preliminary analyses. First, separate CFAs were conducted for each scale, and the fit indices indicated adequate construct validity. Since total scores would be used for scales with sub-dimensions, a second-order factor analysis was applied. In the second step, the full measurement model including all scales was tested, yielding adequate fit indices. The detailed results of the validity and reliability analyses were presented in Table 1.

While some AVE values were slightly below the ideal .50 threshold (ranging from .40 to .49), all CR values were exceptionally strong, ranging from .84 to .95. According to Fornell and Larcker (1981), if AVE is less than .50 but CR is greater than .60, the convergent validity of the construct is still considered adequate. Furthermore, discriminant validity was rigorously evaluated using the Fornell-Larcker criterion. The square root of the AVE for each construct (ranging from .63 to .70) was strictly greater than its highest respective inter-construct

correlation (the absolute maximum correlation being .47 between social media addiction and need for social approval). This fully satisfies the criterion, confirming that all variables represent distinct theoretical concepts.

Table 1

Reliability and Validity Results of the Scales

Scale	Factors	$\chi^2(df)$	CFI	TLI	SRMR	RMSEA	α	CR	AVE
SMAS		439(251)	.93	.92	.050	.050	.94	.95	.44
	Deprivation						.91	.91	.42
	Uncontrollability						.89	.83	.46
Extraversion		34(13)	.96	.94	.034	.073	.87	.87	.49
NFSAS		470(272)	.91	.90	.053	.049	.94	.95	.42
	Sensitivity to others' judgments						.87	.88	.47
	Social withdrawal						.82	.83	.38
	Leaving a good impression						.86	.86	.42
PWBS		58.9(20)	.87	.82	.057	.080	.84	.84	.40
Full measurement model		2334(1940)	.92	.92	.062	.026			

Note. SMAS = Social Media Addiction Scale. NFSAS = Need for Social Approval Scale. PWBS = Psychological Well-Being Scale. α = Cronbach's alpha. CR = composite reliability. AVE = Average Variance Extracted.

While some AVE values were slightly below the ideal .50 threshold (ranging from .40 to .49), all CR values were exceptionally strong, ranging from .84 to .95. According to Fornell and Larcker (1981), if AVE is less than .50 but CR is greater than .60, the convergent validity of the construct is still considered adequate. Furthermore, discriminant validity was rigorously evaluated using the Fornell-Larcker criterion. The square root of the AVE for each construct (ranging from .63 to .70) was strictly greater than its highest respective inter-construct correlation (the absolute maximum correlation being .47 between social media addiction and need for social approval). This fully satisfies the criterion, confirming that all variables represent distinct theoretical concepts.

Descriptive Statistics and Correlations

The distribution characteristics of the study variables can be seen in Figure 1. The correlations are detailed in Table 2. The analysis indicated a positive link between SMA and the NFSAS. In contrast, SMA showed a negative association with PWB. Similarly, higher levels of NFSAS

were associated with lower levels of PWB. Extraversion was negatively related to both SMA and NFSA but positively related to PWB. It is important to note, however, that while these correlations were statistically significant, the strength of the relationships was generally weak.

Table 2

Descriptive Statistics and Correlations Among Study Variables

	Social media addiction	Need for social approval	Extraversion	Psychological well-being	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
Social media addiction	–				2.91	.69
Need for social approval	.474***	–			2.98	.64
Extraversion	-.093	-.283***	–		3.43	.78
Psychological well-being	-.196***	-.138*	-.333***	–	5.32	.85

Note. Pearson correlation coefficients are reported. *** $p < .001$

Figure 1

Distribution of the Study Variables

Note. The figure displays combined violin and box plots. The box represents the interquartile range (Q1-Q3), the central line indicates the median, and the square marker represents the mean. Jittered points display individual participant scores. Scales are presented on their original metrics: The Psychological Well-Being Scale ranges from 1 to 7, whereas all other constructs range from 1 to 5.

Moderation Analyses

Preliminary analyses confirmed that multicollinearity was not an issue, with all Variance

Inflation Factors (VIF) ranging from 1.12 to 2.45 after mean-centering the variables.

Additionally, in accordance with standard moderation procedures (Hayes, 2013, p. 313), unstandardized coefficients are reported.

The main analysis examined how the NFSA and EXT moderate the relationship between SMA and PWB. To test this model, OLS regression-based moderation analyses and simple slope tests were performed using the “GAMLj3” module in JAMOVI (Version 2.4.14). The results indicated that SMA significantly interacts with both the NFSA and EXT. The detailed statistical results of these regression analyses were listed in Table 3.

Table 3

Results of the Moderation Analysis Predicting Psychological Well-Being

Variables	Estimate	SE	95% CI		VIF	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	η^2_p
			Lower	Upper				
Model 1								
SMA	-0.231	.076	-0.380	-0.082	1.293	-3.048	.003	.030
NFSA	0.057	.084	-0.108	0.223	1.393	0.680	.497	.002
EXT	0.360	.062	0.239	0.482	1.090	5.859	< .001	.103
$R^2 = .14, F = 16.20, p < .001$								
Model 2								
SMA	-0.250	.076	-0.399	-0.102	1.307	-3.314	.001	.036
NFSA	0.065	.083	-0.099	0.229	1.396	0.778	.437	.002
EXT	0.366	.061	0.246	0.486	1.095	5.985	< .001	.107
SMA x NFSA	-0.212	.093	-0.396	-0.028	1.134	-2.269	.024	.017
SMA x EXT	-0.181	.084	-0.346	-0.016	1.131	-2.162	.031	.015
$R^2 = .16, F = 11.37, p < .001$								
$\Delta R^2 = .021, \Delta F = 3.69, p = .026$								

Note. SMA = Social Media Addiction. NFSA = Need for Social Approval. EXT = Extraversion. PWB = Psychological Well-Being

To interpret the nature of the significant interactions, simple slope analyses were performed. Following the recommendations of Hayes (2013, p. 250), the 16th, 50th, and 84th percentiles were selected to define “relatively low”, “moderate”, and “relatively high” levels for the variables. The estimates derived from these analyses were presented in Table 4.

Further examination of the findings indicates that the relationship between SMA and PWB changes depending on the levels of EXT and NFSA. For individuals with low extraversion, the relationship was found to be statistically significant only when the NFSA was high. At moderate levels of EXT, the negative relationship was significant for those with either moderate or high NFSA. Most notably, for individuals with high extraversion, the relationship was significantly negative under all conditions, regardless of whether their NFSA was low or high. These interaction patterns were visually presented in Figure 2.

Table 4

Simple Slope Estimates for the Relationship Between Social Media Addiction and Psychological Well-Being At Different Moderator Levels

Moderators		Estimate	SE	95% CI		t	p
EXT	NFSA			Lower	Upper		
16% = 2.57	16% = 2.32	0.044	.127	-0.205	0.294	0.349	.728
	50% = 3.00	-0.100	.101	-0.299	0.099	-0.987	.325
	84% = 3.60	-0.227	.109	-0.441	-0.013	-2.087	.038
50% = 3.57	16% = 2.32	-0.137	.091	-0.316	0.042	-1.503	.134
	50% = 3.00	-0.281	.077	-0.433	-0.129	-3.630	<.001
	84% = 3.60	-0.408	.103	-0.611	-0.205	-3.950	<.001
84% = 4.14	16% = 2.32	-0.240	.101	-0.438	-0.042	-2.389	.018
	50% = 3.00	-0.384	.099	-0.580	-0.189	-3.875	<.001
	84% = 3.60	-0.512	.128	-0.763	-0.260	-4.007	<.001

Note. NFSA = Need for Social Approval. EXT = Extraversion.

Figure 2

Simple Slopes of Social Media Addiction on Psychological Well-Being Across Levels of Extraversion and Need for Social Approval

Note. The plots illustrate the relationship between social media addiction and well-being conditioned on the 16th (low), 50th (moderate), and 84th (high) percentiles of the moderator variables.

Discussion

The primary objective of this study was to examine how personality traits and social motives shape the relationship between social media addiction and psychological well-being. The findings confirmed the main prediction: as social media addiction increases, psychological well-being significantly decreases. This result aligns with the I-PACE model (Brand et al., 2016), which posits that addictive behaviors result in diminished daily functioning and emotional distress. It is also consistent with a vast body of meta-analytic evidence showing that problematic use erodes life satisfaction by fostering anxiety, depression, and social

isolation (Marino et al., 2018; Twenge & Campbell, 2019). However, the unique contribution of this study lies not in this main effect, but in revealing *for whom* this usage is most detrimental. The interaction analyses demonstrated that the impact of addiction is strictly conditional on the user's need for social approval and extraversion. It is important to note, however, that while these interactions significantly predict psychological well-being, the observed effect sizes are relatively small ($\Delta R^2 = .021$). This suggests that although these psychological factors play a role in shaping well-being, they represent only a fraction of the complex array of variables that contribute to an individual's overall psychological health.

Regarding the need for social approval, the results supported the first hypothesis. The negative relationship between addiction and well-being was found to be much steeper for individuals with a high need for social approval. This finding can be explained through social comparison theory. Individuals with a high need for approval are more prone to engage in upward social comparisons, viewing others' curated lives as superior to their own (Vogel et al., 2014). For these users, social media becomes a "validation marketplace" rather than a communication tool. As noted by Jiang and Ngien (2020), when validation-seeking individuals do not receive the expected feedback (likes, comments), they experience higher levels of anxiety. The results support this view, indicating that high-approval seekers rely heavily on unstable external feedback, a dependency that diminishes their psychological resilience (Karaşar & Öğülmüş, 2016).

Furthermore, these specific findings regarding the need for social approval must be interpreted within the cultural context of the current sample. Türkiye is traditionally characterized by a collectivistic cultural orientation, where interpersonal harmony, group belongingness, and social validation are highly prioritized (Kagitcibasi, 2007). In such cultural settings, the need for social approval is not merely an individual personality trait, but a deeply ingrained cultural expectation. Consequently, the severe negative impact of social

media addiction on the well-being of high-approval seekers observed in this study might be particularly amplified by this collectivistic backdrop. For these individuals, failing to achieve digital validation may represent a profound threat to their perceived social standing. In highly individualistic cultures, where self-worth is relatively more independent of external group validation, this specific interaction might yield different psychological outcomes. Therefore, it is highly recommended that future cross-cultural studies replicate this model to determine the global generalizability of these moderation effects.

The second critical finding concerns Extraversion. Conflicting views exist in the literature: the “Rich-Get-Richer” hypothesis argues that extraverts benefit from online tools, while the social displacement hypothesis argues they lose out. The results strongly support the social displacement hypothesis (Kraut et al., 1998). It was found that the negative association between social media addiction and well-being is significantly stronger for highly extraverted individuals compared to introverts. Extraverts naturally thrive on synchronous, face-to-face social energy and sensory feedback (Gençöz & Öncül, 2012). When addictive scrolling displaces these vital offline interactions, the psychological “opportunity cost” is far higher for an extravert than for an introvert, who may typically prefer lower-stimulation environments. This mirrors the findings of Primack et al. (2017), who suggested that for sociable individuals, replacing real-world ties with digital ones leads to a paradoxical sense of social isolation.

Furthermore, the parallel interaction patterns reveal compounding vulnerabilities. As visualized in the respective simple slope analyses, both a high need for social approval and high extraversion independently exacerbate the negative association between social media addiction and well-being. Within the framework of the I-PACE model, this suggests that users possessing both “Person” characteristics (high extraversion and high approval need) may conceptually face additive risks (Brand et al., 2019). This creates a cumulative negative effect: their extraversion drives a hunger for connection that screens cannot truly satisfy

(displacement), while their need for approval makes them vulnerable to the endless comparison cycle.

Limitations and Future Directions

These findings should be interpreted within the context of several limitations. First and foremost, the study employed a cross-sectional design, which precludes making causal inferences. While the theoretical model assumes that addiction drives lower well-being, it is also plausible that individuals with lower well-being seek solace in social media, as suggested by the compensatory internet use theory (Kardefelt-Winther, 2014). Future studies employing longitudinal or experimental designs would be better positioned to clarify the directionality of these effects. Second, the data were collected via self-report measures, which are susceptible to social desirability bias. Future research could benefit from integrating objective log data (e.g., actual screen time) to validate subjective reports. Third, psychological well-being was assessed using a single self-report measure (i.e., the Psychological Well-Being Scale). Given that well-being is a complex and multifaceted construct, its measurement model yielded marginal fit indices in the current sample. To preserve the scale's content validity and original theoretical structure, items were not omitted, though this represents a measurement limitation. It is important to note that different measurement tools might yield varying patterns of associations, as the operationalization of the construct can influence study outcomes, and indeed, various studies in the literature have employed alternative assessment methods (Arpacık et al., 2025; Kiremitçi Caniöz & Coşkun; 2018; Kiremitçi-Caniöz et al., 2025; Okudur Sabuncu et al., 2023). Additionally, as highlighted by the effect sizes, the explanatory power of the tested model is limited ($\Delta R^2 = .16$). Future research should incorporate additional environmental, biological, and individual variables to build more comprehensive models. Finally, the sample consisted of university students in Türkiye. To improve the generalizability of the findings, future studies should replicate this model across different age

groups and cultural contexts, particularly in cultures with different collectivist or individualist orientations regarding social approval.

Conclusion

Overall, the current study provides strong evidence that the digital well-being equation is highly personalized. The results indicate that social media addiction is not equally harmful to everyone; rather, its toxicity is amplified by specific personality traits and social motives. By identifying extraverted individuals with a high need for social approval as a specific “high-risk” profile, this study suggests that clinical and preventive interventions should move beyond a “one-size-fits-all” approach. However, given the small effect sizes observed, these interventions should be viewed as supplementary components of broader mental health programs rather than primary solutions. Practitioners should exercise caution and avoid overestimating the impact of social media-related factors alone. Instead, strategies should focus on helping these vulnerable individuals reconnect with offline sources of validation and interaction to break the cycle of digital dependency within a holistic therapeutic framework.

Conflict of interests:

The author has no conflict of interest to declare.

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Ethics Committee Approval:

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Declaration of AI Use in Scientific Writing: In the preparation of this study, the author utilized Gemini Pro for the purpose of English language editing and proofreading to enhance the clarity of the text. After using this tool/service, the author has reviewed and edited the content as needed and takes full responsibility for the content of the publication

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